

Optimization of Hobby Aircraft Configuration

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Hobby level aircraft design can be a tedious and iterative process. To ease the design process, a function is developed and optimized for hobby aircraft energy usage based on aircraft aspect ratio, coefficient of lift, span, motor throttle, and battery capacity. The function allows for specification of mission range, required payload, motor size, and battery voltage which enables energy calculations for a variety of mission profiles. The function is optimized with the MATLAB gradient-based fmincon constrained optimizer. The optimum configurations for a variety of missions are reported and explored. Results from optimization agree with hobby aircraft design best practices and rules of thumb.

I. Introduction

MODEL aircraft have become a popular learning tool for exploring principles of aerodynamics and aircraft design in university courses. These small scale aircraft offer cheap and low risk opportunities to exercise real design practices in hands-on projects. Students gain experience performing basic aerodynamic calculations, structural analysis, and electronics selection. Manufacturing the aircraft teaches lessons about tolerances, thoughtful design decisions, and materials selection. The thrill of flight and the challenge of design appeal to many students, some of whom go on to make designing model aircraft a life-long hobby.

As those familiar with aircraft design know, the design process can be extremely iterative. The designer generally begins with a rough idea for a mission profile and desired performance. Initial sizing of the aircraft to achieve the desired performance is generally based on intuition or prior experience. Various aspects of this initial design are then altered as the design gets fine tuned in consecutive attempts to improve performance or fulfill mission objectives. This process can become tedious and less than enjoyable as the number of iterations increases.

This type of problem, one with repeated iterations in search of an optimum, can be effectively solved using optimization techniques. These techniques use complex algorithms to explore a multidimensional design space and return optimum configurations within that space. The application of optimization techniques to small aircraft design is not new. Thu et al explored the optimization of aircraft configuration while minimizing drag [1]. Ragot et al optimized an electric motor for a solar airplane configuration [2]. Alonso et al and Kontigiannis et al both performed optimization on a more complete configuration of small unmanned aircraft [3, 4].

While each of the mentioned works presents important findings for the optimization of small unmanned aircraft,

each focuses on a limited aspect of the aircraft configuration or on the application of complex modeling methods, such as the inclusion of computational fluid dynamics solvers. The level of detail and complexity of such projects exceed the requirements for hobby level aircraft design. The current work aims to perform a simpler and slightly more comprehensive optimization of a small aircraft, targeted to hobby aircraft designers. The optimization presented assists the hobby aircraft designer by reducing the number of iterations required to size key aspects of the aircraft in the search for an optimal design that meets mission requirements. As such, the optimization relies on simple expressions a hobby-level designer would be familiar with and allows for versatile mission definitions.

The formulation of the objective function used in the optimization is laid out and details regarding the optimization problem and associated solver are presented. The objective of the optimization will be to minimize the energy used in flight. A baseline mission is optimized and the resulting optimal configuration is explored. In order to determine that the optimization process is robust across various mission profiles, a series of mission cases are optimized and the results compared to ensure expected changes in the optimum configuration correspond with what is expected based on intuition.

II. Methodology

A. Objective Function Formulation

In order to optimize the aircraft configuration, the key relationships which impact performance must be defined in an objective function. This function is what will be minimized during the optimization process. The objective function for this work was developed to include several important aerodynamic and power relationships which impact aircraft efficiency. The basic structure and equations used in the objective function are laid out in the following paragraphs.

The objective function takes aspect ratio (AR), span (b), coefficient of lift (C_L), battery energy, and throttle percentage as inputs and returns the energy required to fly a specified mission with the input configuration. Mission parameters are defined within the function and include required range, available motor power, payload weight, and battery voltage. These can be varied to simulate a variety of mission requirements.

AR and b impact the sizing of the wing, which each play a large role in flight efficiency. The planform area of the wing (S) is calculated using Equation 1 and the provided values for AR and b . With this wing size value, we begin to explore the basic aerodynamics of the aircraft.

$$S = \frac{b^2}{AR} \quad (1)$$

C_L connects the lift of the aircraft with the velocity and is defined in Equation 2, where L is the lift required by the weight of the plane structure, ρ is air density, and V is the velocity of the aircraft. The lift required for the aircraft is determined by calculating the weight of the aircraft. This weight includes scaling estimates which account for electronics sizing and wing sizing. Equation 2 is solved for velocity, which is used later to estimate drag and power values.

$$C_L = \frac{2L}{\rho V^2 S} \quad (2)$$

Coefficient of drag (C_D) is then calculated, using Equation 3, where C_{D0} refers to the parasitic drag coefficient and e is the Oswald Span Efficiency factor. For this problem C_{D0} was calculated using Equation 4 and an e of 1 was assumed. Equation 4 allows for variation of C_{D0} due to V through Reynolds Number (Re) and due to wing sizing through the wetted planform area S_{wet} .

$$C_D = C_{D0} + \frac{C_L^2}{\pi e AR} \quad (3)$$

$$C_{D0} = \left(\frac{0.075}{Re^{1/5}} + 0.01 \right) S_{wet} \quad (4)$$

Drag (D) is then estimated using Equation 5. Combined with V , this enables an estimate for power required to be calculated. This power required value is then scaled using motor and propeller efficiencies to determine the power draw of the motor to produce the required power. Motor efficiency scales using a quadratic with the throttle percentage, approximating a motor efficiency curve. This is then used to estimate the energy required to fly the required range distance, which is the output of the function.

$$D = 1/2 C_D \rho V^2 S \quad (5)$$

Assumptions in this methodology include an elliptical lift distribution without considering effects of taper, sweep, or twist. Sizing and effects of additional lifting surfaces (e.g. empennage, canard) are not considered, nor is any structural or stability analysis included.

B. Optimization Formulation

The optimization problem is formally defined as follows.

Minimize: Energy used in flight over a set distance

With respect to: AR , b , C_L , motor throttle, battery capacity

Subject to: $0 \leq AR \leq 12$

$0 \leq b$

$0.1 \leq C_L \leq 1$

$0.15 \leq \text{average chord } (c)$

$V \leq 30$

Power required \leq motor power

$$\text{Energy required for motor} \leq \text{energy available in battery}$$

In summary, the energy required to fly the required range is minimized. This is accomplished by altering the five listed design variables subject to the constraints specified. These constraints are vital in keeping the function in feasible space, as they represent realistic bounds due to manufacturability and wing design. In order to increase optimization stability, parameters were scaled to be of the same magnitude. This ensured that the optimizer properly explored the design space freely without being biased by larger magnitude parameters.

Several optimization algorithms were explored for solving the defined optimization problem. The first algorithm explored was MATLAB’s `fmincon` function, which is a solver for constrained optimization problems available with MATLAB’s optimization toolbox. It uses gradient-based methods for determining the minimum of a provided function. A second constrained gradient-based optimizer developed by the authors was also tested with this problem. This in-house optimizer used unconstrained optimization with an exterior point penalty method to enforce constraints. Though it reached the same optimum values as the `fmincon` algorithm, it did so in a significantly less efficient manner by requiring additional time and function calls to converge. Finally, a gradient free algorithm was tested. The algorithm selected was a 3rd party algorithm, called `GODLIKE`, which combines genetic and particle swarm methods to solve optimization problems [5]. In its current form, `GODLIKE` does not enforce constraints, so a basic penalty method was applied. This resulted in a less than stable optimizer which did not regularly converge to the feasible optimums. Considering all three optimizers together, the `fmincon` optimizer was selected due to its efficiency and robustness.

Each optimization was started at the following initial conditions.

Table 1 Initial conditions used for optimizing the function.

Design Variable	Initial Value
AR	1.0
b (m)	1.0
C_L	0.10
Throttle (%)	50
Battery Capacity (mA-h)	2200

`Fmincon` was configured to use the active-set algorithm. The optimality tolerance and constraint tolerance were set to be $1E-6$, with a limit of 1000 iterations and 10,000 functions calls. The default forward-differencing approximations for gradients built in to `fmincon` was used. The code provided as an appendix to this work was used to run each optimization and includes definitions for the objective function, constraints, and bounds.

III. Results

A. Baseline Mission

Parameters for the baseline case were chosen to replicate an average mission and capabilities for a standard model aircraft. Table 2 gives the mission parameters used for this baseline case.

Table 2 Values chosen as mission requirements for the baseline case study.

Mission Parameter	Value
Range (km)	50
Motor Size (W)	300
Payload (kg)	0.6
Battery Size (V)	11.1

Optimizing the function with these mission parameters yielded the optimal design variable values shown in Table 3. These values confirm that the problem function was implemented correctly and that the applied constraints allow the optimizer to find a realistic solution within a feasible design space.

Table 3 Optimized output values for design variables for the baseline mission configuration.

Design Variable	Optimized Value
AR	10.3
b (m)	1.54
C_L	0.58
Throttle (%)	16
Battery Capacity (mA-h)	3112
Velocity (m/s)	19.7

It is noteworthy that the optimizer finds a desirably high aspect ratio to reduce the energy used. The chord (derived from the aspect ratio and span) is reduced to its lower limit due to the lack of accounting for the effect this has on bending stress, and the remainder of the variables settle to values appropriate for a model aircraft in a cruising configuration.

B. Mission Case Studies

Finding that the optimized baseline mission yielded satisfactory results, various case studies were performed to adjust mission parameters and observe the resulting effect on the solution. Table 4 outlines the various cases and their respective mission parameters and design variable outputs. Note that each case generally changes from the baseline by doubling or halving a single mission parameter at a time.

These results demonstrate that an optimized solution is achievable under a myriad of mission parameters, recommending an aircraft configuration that is physically realistic to manufacture. It is also observed from these case studies that the optimizer is able to work with the problem function in a way that reflects principles and intuition

Table 4 Mission parameters and resulting optimized design variables for eight case studies as varied from the baseline mission configuration.

Case	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Range (km)	100	25	50	50	50	50	50	50
Motor Size (W)	300	300	600	150	300	300	300	300
Payload (kg)	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	1.2	0.3	0.6	0.6
Battery Size (V)	11.1	11.1	11.1	11.1	11.1	11.1	14.8	7.4
AR	12.0	6.2	6.7	12.0	11.9	5.1	7.5	12.0
b (m)	1.81	0.93	1.01	1.80	1.79	0.77	1.12	1.80
C_L	0.80	0.34	0.38	0.73	0.84	0.28	0.42	0.70
Throttle (%)	23	21	12	36	53	14	20	22
Battery Capacity (mA-h)	9117	1297	2898	3925	8895	1691	2137	6529
Velocity (m/s)	19.5	30.0	30.0	17.0	22.4	30.0	25.9	19.2

involved with aircraft design. Namely, as mission difficulty increases (i.e. range or payload is increased or motor size is decreased) the optimized aircraft becomes more and more aerodynamically efficient with a higher aspect ratio and cruise lift coefficient. These cases also demonstrated similar or lower cruise velocities despite increased mission difficulty. Conversely, as mission difficulty decreased, not only did the aircraft rely on less efficient means of mission completion, it would often switch to a "sprinting" mentality where it increased the velocity to try to decrease the time spent on the mission as far as possible.

IV. Conclusion

The formulated objective function, used in conjunction with the MATLAB optimizer `fmincon`, is successful in suggesting an aircraft configuration sufficient and optimal for completing a specified mission. The scope of this function allows for simple and approachable preliminary analysis by the hobby aircraft designer for a first pass configuration. Additional iterations for a true aircraft design are still required, as the function still does not account for structural loading or additional flight conditions beyond cruise. However, the configuration provided by this objective function allows for a significant reduction in the number of iterations and work required by the hobbyist.

Students and others looking to explore the inter-dependent nature of aircraft parameters and equations may use this function to conduct their own trade studies and observe the variability of various parameters. It is hoped that this may reduce the tedious aspect of iterative aircraft design and free the designer to explore additional configurations that go beyond the scope of this work. As the interested designer masters the fundamentals encapsulated by this function, they may apply its principles to more complex designs (e.g. tapered wings) or expand to include structural or stability analysis.

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